

CALCULATING DISTANCE USING THE JURAVLYOV
METRIC

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the distance between objects in a sample, represented by various features, is calculated using the Juravlyov metric. The program was implemented in Python, and the values were computed.

Numerical methods lie at the core of pattern recognition for classifying patterns. A pattern is a set of features derived from the input data [1]. The operation of pattern recognition systems is divided into two stages:

1. Extracting features from the input (numerical) data and forming patterns based on them.

2. Classifying the patterns, i.e., assigning them to one, two, or more classes.

Any pattern can be described by an ordered set of numbers, where each number represents the value of a certain feature. These values may not correspond directly to the real values of the features they represent; they could be the result of scaling, normalization, or other types of transformations.

From a mathematical perspective, a pattern is equivalent to a vector, representing a point in hyperspace.

If there are n features, the pattern vectors are considered n -dimensional and occupy an n -dimensional space, or hyperspace. In general, a feature X is represented as follows:

$$X = [x_1, \dots, x_n, 1]^T$$

The image space can be represented by a vector of \mathbf{n} vectors — the matrix \mathbf{X} . Within the image space, images can be imagined as a hyperphase of scattered points representing them.

Let us consider a set of objects divided into \mathbf{l} mutually disjoint classes K_1, \dots, K_l . The objects are described by a set of \mathbf{t} attributes of different types, some of which are nominal and some measured on a quantitative scale. We will examine these two types of attributes more closely.

A **nominal attribute** is a characteristic that indicates the category or name of an object. Mathematical operations cannot be performed on nominal attributes. They are not measured numerically and only indicate a named category (for example, gender: male or female).

A **quantitative attribute** is a measurable characteristic expressed numerically (for example, height 156.7).

When both nominal and quantitative attributes are present in a sample, and the distance between objects needs to be calculated, we use the **Juravlyov metric**.

Let $E_0 = \{S_1, \dots, S_m\}$ be a training sample divided into l mutually disjoint classes K_1, \dots, K_l . In the sample, each object $S \in E_0$ is described by n attributes of different types. The **Juravlyov metric** is calculated using the following formula [6]:

$$\rho(x, y) = \sum_{j \in I} |x_j - y_j| + \sum_{j \in J} \begin{cases} 1, & x_j \neq y_j, \\ 0, & x_j = y_j. \end{cases}$$

Here, X_q and X_n denote the sets of indices for quantitative and nominal features, respectively. To unify the measurement scales, the values of quantitative features are mapped to the $[0,1]$ interval using linear fractional transformation.

We calculate this metric using samples from Uzbek and Korean populations. In this sample, there are no quantitative features; it contains 34 nominal features, with the first feature being the classification feature. The sample was formed based on a survey of 100 individuals from two different nationalities. Briefly, the given data are as follows:

1. **Nationality** {Uzbek; Korean}
2. **What do you feel when faced with an unexpected obstacle?** {Irritation; Self-pity; Anxiety, fear; Tension, focus}
3. **Your gender?** {female; male}

The results obtained from the above survey are presented in Table 1.

Nationality | How do I feel when faced with an unexpected obstacle? | Your gender?

1 | 3 | 1
 1 | 1 | 1
 1 | 4 | 2
 1 | 4 | 1
 1 | 2 | 2
 1 | 3 | 2
 2 | 1 | 1
 2 | 4 | 2
 2 | 4 | 2
 2 | 3 | 1
 2 | 4 | 1

When performing operations on the complete sample and calculating the metric, the results obtained are shown in the table below (Table 2):

Objects	Distances obtained using the Juravlyov metric					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	0	28	26	27	23	27
2	28	0	27	27	28	26
3	26	27	0	28	25	28
4	27	27	28	0	27	24
5	23	28	25	27	0	29

Objects	Distances obtained using the Juravlyov metric					
6	27	26	28	24	29	0

As seen from Table 2, when the distance is calculated between an object and itself, the value is **0**. In other cases, the results are integers because for nominal attributes, a match in gradation contributes 0 to the distance, while a mismatch adds 1.

The advantage of this metric is that it can be applied to different types of attributes and helps to determine distances more accurately.

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